

On Conformal Transformation of Lagrange Space with (γ, β) -Metric

Lal Chandra¹, Ganga Prasad Yadav²,

^{1,2}Department of Mathematics

Nehru Gram Bharati (Deemed To Be University)

Allahabad-211505, India

lal9026153385@gmail.com, ORCID-0000-0002-0251-9856,

Abstract

The present paper is a study of the conformal transformation of the Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metric. The conformal transformation of the spray coefficient and Riemann curvature are expressed in Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metric. Further, find out the condition that a conformal transformation of Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metric is locally dually flat if and only if the transformation is a homothety. Moreover, the conditions for the transform metrics to be Einstein and isotropic mean Berwald curvature are also found.

Key words: Conformal transformation, Homothety, Lagrange space, Locally dually flat, (γ, β) -metric.

2010 Mathematics subject classification: 53B40, 53A40 53C60.

1 Introduction

M. Matsumoto has been studied the non-Riemannian Finsler space with a cubic metric in 1979 [4]. A cubic metric is defined as, [7]

$$(1.1) \quad L(x, y) = \left\{ a_{ijk}(x) y^i y^j y^k \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}}.$$

where $a_{ijk}(x)$ are components of a symmetric tensor field of $(0, 3)$ -type depending on the position x alone.

The β metric defined as,

$$(1.2) \quad \beta(x, y) = b_i(x)y^i,$$

where $b_i(x)$ are components of a covariant vector in space.

Pandey and Chaubey introduced the concept of (γ, β) -metric In 2011, where $\gamma = \left\{ a_{ijk}(x)y^i y^j y^k \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}}$ is cubic metric and $\beta = b_i(x)y^i$ is a one-form. P.N. Pandey and S.K. Shukla studied Lagrange space with (γ, β) metric and obtained metric tensor in L^n Lagrange space. In 2006 L. Tamassy studied the relation between Lagrange and Finsler space and established that the Hessians $H_{ij}(x, y)$ are positive definite if and only if the hyper-surface $z^{I(x)}$ are convex.

Matsomoto has been developed the theory of Finsler spaces [9] and the theory of conformal transformation of Finsler spaces has been developed by M. Hashiguchi[10] based on the theory of Finsler space. Let F and \bar{F} be two Finsler metrics on manifold M^n then we say that Finsler metric \bar{F} conformally transformed Finsler metric[11] if $\bar{F} = e^{\alpha(x)}F$ where α is a scalar function on M^n . The conformal change is said to be a homothety if α is a constant.

2 Preliminaries

Let M be an n -dimensional smooth manifold and let TM be its tangent bundle. Let (x^i) and (x^i, y^i) be local coordinates on M and TM , respectively. A Lagrangian is a function $L : TM \rightarrow R$ which is a smooth function on $\tilde{TM} = TM \setminus \{0\}$ and continuous on the null section.

The fundamental metric tensor of Lagrangian $L(x, y)$ is given by $g_{ij}(x, y)$ and define as,

$$(2.1) \quad g_{ij}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j L^2,$$

where $\dot{\partial}_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial y^i}$.

Definition 2.1. A Lagrange space is a pair $L^n = (M, L(x, y))$. The metric tensor g_{ij} of Lagrangian $L(x, y)$ being a constant signature on \tilde{TM} is called a regular Lagrangian.

In the present paper, we study a Lagrange space whose Lagrangian L is a function of $\gamma(x, y)$ and $\beta(x, y)$ only, where

$$(2.2) \quad \begin{cases} a) \gamma^3(x, y) = a_{ijk}(x, y)y^i y^j y^k \\ b) \beta(x, y) = b_i(x)y^i. \end{cases}$$

On Conformal Transformation of Lagrange Space with (γ, β) -Metric

Let us denote the conformal transform Lagrangian by \bar{L} . Thus the conformal transform Lagrange metric given by

$$(2.3) \quad \bar{L}(\gamma, \beta) = e^{\alpha(x)} L(x, y).$$

The space $L^n = (M, L(x, y))$ is called space with (γ, β) -metric [2]. The fundamental metric [1] of $L^n = (M, L(x, y))$ defined as,

$$(2.4) \quad g_{ij}(x, y) = 2\rho a_{ij} + \rho_{-2} a_i a_j + \rho_{-1} (a_i b_j + b_i a_j) + \rho_0 b_i b_j.$$

where ρ, ρ_0 and ρ_{-1}, ρ_{-2} given as

$$(2.5) \quad \begin{cases} a) \rho = \frac{1}{2} \gamma^{-2} L_{\gamma\gamma}, \\ b) \rho_0 = \frac{1}{2} L_{\beta\beta}, \\ c) \rho_{-1} = \frac{1}{2} \gamma^{-2} L_{\gamma\beta}, \\ d) \rho_{-2} = \frac{1}{2} \gamma^{-4} (L_{\gamma\gamma} - 2\gamma^{-1} L_{\gamma}). \end{cases}$$

The normalize supporting element l_i and angular metric tensor h_{ij} of L are defined respectively as: $l_i = \frac{\partial L}{\partial y^i}, h_{ij} = L \frac{\partial^2 L^2}{\partial y^i \partial y^j}$.

Definition 2.2. A Finsler metric $L(x, y)$ is called a (γ, β) -metric. If L is a positive homogeneous function of first degree in two variable γ and β . Where $\gamma^3 = a_{ijk} y^i y^j y^k$ is a cubic metric and $\beta = b_i(x) y^i$ is a one form.

Definition 2.3. The Lagrangian metric $L(\gamma, \beta)$ -metric will be Finsler metric if following conditions hold [8]

$$(2.6) \quad p_{-1} + q_{-2} \beta + q_{-1} \gamma^3 = 0,$$

$$(2.7) \quad q_0 \beta + q_{-2} \gamma^3 = 0,$$

where $p_{-1} = \frac{LL_{\gamma\gamma}}{2}, q_0 = LL_{\beta\beta}, q_{-2} = \frac{LL_{\gamma\beta}}{\gamma^2}, q_{-1} = \frac{L}{\gamma^4} (L_{\gamma\gamma} - \frac{2L_{\gamma}}{\gamma})$.

The subscripts of coefficient $p_{-1}, q_0, q_{-2}, q_{-1}$ indicate respectively degree of homogeneity.

3 Conformal transformation Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metric

The fundamental metric tensor g_{ij} of Lagrange space L^n is given by

$$(3.1) \quad g_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 L^2}{\partial y^i \partial y^j} = LL_{y^i y^j} - L_{y^i} L_{y^j}.$$

From equation (2.4) the metric tensor g_{ij} simplifies as $g_{ij} = 2\rho a_{ij} + c_i c_j$. The conformal transform metric \bar{g}_{ij} is derived as:

$$(3.2) \quad \bar{g}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j \bar{L}^2 = e^{2\alpha} g_{ij}.$$

It is also derived that

$$(3.3) \quad \bar{g}^{ij} = e^{-2\alpha} g^{ij}.$$

Theorem 3.1. *The covariant metric tensor \bar{g}_{ij} and contravariant metric tensor \bar{g}^{ij} of transformed Lagrange space L^n with (γ, β) -metric are given as*

$$(3.4) \quad \bar{g}_{ij} = e^{2\alpha} g_{ij} = e^{2\alpha} (2\rho a_{ij} + c_i c_j),$$

$$(3.5) \quad \bar{g}^{ij} = e^{-2\alpha} g^{mh} = e^{-2\alpha} \frac{1}{2\rho} \left(a^{mh} - \frac{1}{2\rho + c^2} c^m c^h \right).$$

The transformed Christoffel symbols of the first kind written for (γ, β) -metric as,

$$(3.6) \quad [jk, h] = 2e^{2\alpha} \left\{ \alpha_j g_{kh} + \alpha_k g_{jh} - \alpha_h g_{jk} \right\} + e^{2\alpha} [jk, h],$$

Hence the conformal transformed Christoffel's symbols connected with metric tensor as,

$$(3.7) \quad \overline{\left\{ \begin{matrix} m \\ jk \end{matrix} \right\}} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} m \\ jk \end{matrix} \right\} + \left\{ \alpha_j \delta_k^m + \alpha_k \delta_j^m - \alpha_h g^{mh} g_{jk} \right\},$$

The index $m \rightarrow i$ and h is dummy index so take $h = k$. Then the spray coefficient G^i conformal transformed following equation,

$$(3.8) \quad \bar{G}^i = \alpha_j + G^i.$$

If $\alpha_j = 0$, then $\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x^j} = 0 \Rightarrow \alpha = \text{constant}$.

Theorem 3.2. *Let L and \bar{L} conformally related metrics in Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metric. Then the geodesic curves are identical if and only if a conformal change is a homothety.*

Proof. The geodesic equation in Lagrange space is given by

$$(3.9) \quad \frac{d^2 x^i}{ds^2} + \left\{ \begin{matrix} i \\ jk \end{matrix} \right\} \frac{dx^j}{ds} \frac{dx^k}{ds} = 0.$$

On Conformal Transformation of Lagrange Space with (γ, β) -Metric

Let conformal change is homothety, then $\alpha = constant$, hence $\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x^j} = 0$. The equation (3.8) gives that the spray coefficient $\bar{G}^i = G^i$, so Geodesic equation (3.9) is identical after transformation. So the geodesic curve also will be identical. \square

The conformal transform spray G expression is given by

$$(3.10) \quad \bar{G} = G - 2\alpha_j e^\alpha (L_\gamma \gamma y^j + L_\beta b_i).$$

4 Locally dually flat conformally transformed in Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metric

In the study of information geometry on Riemannian manifolds, Amari-Nagaoka developed the notion of dually flat Riemannian metrics [12]. Locally dually flatness for Finsler metrics notion developed by Shen [13].

A transform Finsler metric \bar{F} on a manifold M^n is said to be locally dually flat if $[\bar{F}^2]_{x^k y^l} y^k = 2 [\bar{F}]_{x^l}$ at any point with the coordinate system (x^i, y^i) in TM .

Let the conformal transformation $\bar{L} = e^\alpha L$, where L is Lagrange metric with (γ, β) -metric. Since $\bar{L}_{x^k}^2 = e^{2\alpha} [L_{x^k}^2 + 2L^2 \alpha_k]$, where $\alpha_k = \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x^k}$, we have $\bar{L}_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k = e^{2\alpha} [L_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k + 2L l \alpha_k y^k]$. Hence

$$(4.1) \quad \begin{aligned} L_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k &= 2L_\gamma^2 \frac{a_{ij}(y^i y^j y^k)^2}{3\gamma^2} A_k + 2L_\gamma L_\beta b_l A_k y^i y^j (y^k)^2 + 2LL_{\gamma\gamma} \\ &\times \frac{a_{ij}(y^i y^j y^k)^2}{3\gamma^2} A_k + 2LL_{\gamma\beta} b_l A_k y^i y^j (y^k)^2 - \frac{4}{3\gamma^3} A_k (y^i y^j y^k)^2 y^k \\ &+ 2L_\gamma L_\beta \frac{a_{ij}(y^i y^j y^k)^2}{3\gamma^2} + 2L_\beta^2 b_l B_k (y^k)^2 + 2LL_\beta \frac{a_{ij} y^i y^j (y^k)^2}{3\gamma^2} B_k \\ &+ 2LL_{\beta\beta} b_l B_k (y^k)^2 + 2LL_\beta B_l y^k, \end{aligned}$$

$$(4.2) \quad 2L_{x^l}^2 = 4LL_\gamma y^i y^j y^k A_l + 4LL_\beta B_l y^l,$$

$$(4.3) \quad 2LL_{y^l} \alpha_k y^k = \left(\frac{2}{3\gamma^2} LL_\gamma a_{ij} y^i y^j y^k + 2LL_\beta b_l y^k \right) \alpha_k.$$

We have

$$(4.4) \quad 2\bar{L}_{x^l}^2 - \bar{L}_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k = e^{2\alpha} [2L_{x^l}^2 + 4L^2\alpha_l - L_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k - 2Ll_l\alpha_k y^k].$$

If Lagrange space is locally dually flat then $2L_{x^l}^2 - L_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k = 0$. Using equation (4.1), (4.2) and (4.3) in equation (4.4) we find out that,

$$(4.5) \quad 2\bar{L}_{x^l}^2 - \bar{L}_{x^k y^l}^2 y^k = 4L^2\alpha_l - \left(\frac{2}{3\gamma^2} LL_\gamma a_{ij} y^i y^j + 2LL_\beta b_l \right) \alpha_k y^k.$$

Where terms used in equation (4.1) to (4.4) are defined in the following way,

1. $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial x^k} = A_k y^i y^j y^k,$
2. $\frac{\partial \beta}{\partial x^k} = B_k y^k,$
3. $\frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial y^i \partial x^l} = B_l,$
4. $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial y^l} = \frac{1}{3\gamma^2} a_{ij} y^i y^j.$

Theorem 4.1. *If \bar{L} be a conformal transformed metric with (γ, β) -metric on a manifolds M^n in Lagrange space. Then, \bar{L} is locally dually flat metric if and only if $2L\alpha_l - \left(\frac{1}{3\gamma^2} L_\gamma a_{ij} y^i y^j + L_\beta b_l \right) \alpha_k y^k = 0$.*

Corollary 4.1. *If L is locally dually flat metric then the conformally transformed Lagrangian metric \bar{L} is also locally dually flat if and only if conformal transformation homothetic.*

Proof. Form equation (4.5) the L is locally dually flat if and only $2L\alpha_l - \left(\frac{1}{3\gamma^2} L_\gamma a_{ij} y^i y^j + L_\beta b_l \right) \alpha_k y^k = 0$. Hence \bar{L} is locally dually flat if and only if

$$(4.6) \quad \alpha_l L - \left(\frac{1}{3\gamma^2} L_\gamma a_{ij} y^i y^j + L_\beta b_l \right) \alpha_0 = 0$$

Contracting equation (4.6) with y^l , We have

$$\alpha_0 L - \left(\frac{1}{3} \gamma L_\gamma + L_\beta \beta \right) \alpha_0 = 0$$

This gives $\alpha_0 = 0$. Hence from equation (4.6), $\alpha_l = 0$, i.e. $\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x^l} = 0$. So α is constant. Therefore the transformation is homothetic. The converse is also true. \square

On Conformal Transformation of Lagrange Space with (γ, β) -Metric

5 Conformally transformed Lagrangian (γ, β) -metric with isotropic E -curvature

The Berwald curvature of \bar{L} is defined as

$$(5.1) \quad \bar{B}_{jkl}^i = \frac{\partial^3 \bar{G}^i}{\partial y^j \partial y^k \partial y^l}.$$

Where \bar{G}^i are spray coefficients of a Lagrange space \bar{L} . The trace of the Berwald curvature is called the E -curvature. So $\bar{E}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \bar{B}_{mij}^m$. Let \bar{L} is the Lagrangian metric on an n -dimensional manifold M^n . Then The isotropic mean Berwald curvature or of isotropic E -curvature defined as

$$(5.2) \quad \bar{E}_{ij} = \frac{c(n+1)}{2\bar{L}} \bar{h}_{ij}.$$

where $\bar{h}_{ij} = \bar{g}_{ij} - \bar{l}_i \bar{l}_j$ is the angular metric and $c = c(x)$ is a scalar function on M^n . Now \bar{L} will be weakly Berwald metric if scalar function $c = 0$. In view of equation (3.4) the angular metric is given by

$$(5.3) \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{h}_{ij} = e^{2\alpha} \left\{ \rho a_{ij} + \rho_{-2} a_i a_j + \rho_{-1} (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) + \rho_0 b_i b_j - \frac{L_\gamma^2}{9\gamma^4} a_i a_j \right. \\ \left. - \frac{L_\gamma L_\beta}{3\gamma^2} (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) - L_\beta^2 b_i b_j \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

From equation (5.2) and (5.3), we have

$$(5.4) \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{E}_{ij} = \frac{(n+1)c}{2\bar{L}} e^{2\alpha} \left\{ \rho a_{ij} + \rho_{-2} a_i a_j + \rho_{-1} (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) + \rho_0 b_i b_j \right. \\ \left. - \frac{L_\gamma^2}{9\gamma^4} a_i a_j - \frac{L_\gamma L_\beta}{3\gamma^2} (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) - L_\beta^2 b_i b_j \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

After simplification the equation (5.4) we have

$$(5.5) \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{E}_{ij} = \frac{(n+1)c}{2\bar{L}} e^\alpha \left\{ \rho a_{ij} + \left(\rho_{-2} - \frac{L_\gamma^2}{9\gamma^4} \right) a_i a_j + \left(\rho_{-1} - \frac{L_\gamma L_\beta}{3\gamma^2} \right) \right. \\ \left. (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) + (\rho_0 - L_\beta^2) b_i b_j \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

The equation (5.5) shows that $c = 0$, because neither $e^\alpha = 0$ nor $\rho a_{ij} + \left(\rho_{-2} - \frac{L_\gamma^2}{9\gamma^4} \right) a_i a_j + \left(\rho_{-1} - \frac{L_\gamma L_\beta}{3\gamma^2} \right) (a_i b_j + a_j b_i) + (\rho_0 - L_\beta^2) b_i b_j = 0$, i.e. $h_{ij} \neq 0$. Hence the isotropic E -curvature $\bar{E}_{ij} = 0$.

Theorem 5.1. *If $\bar{L} = e^c L$ be the conformal change of Lagrangian metric L . Suppose \bar{L} has isotropic mean Berwald curvature. Then it reduced to a weakly Berwald metric.*

6 Conclusion

The article starts with a basic definition of cubic and β metrics with the formulation of Lagrange space with (γ, β) -metrics. The next part of the article gives a conformal change of Lagrangian metrics and locally dually flat change in Lagrange space. There are some results on isotropic E -curvature.

References

- [1] S. K. Shukla and P. N. Pandey,(2013), Lagrange Spaces with (γ, β) -Metric, *Hindawi Publishing Corporation.*, 1-7,<https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/106393>.
- [2] V. K. Tripathi,(2014), Finslerian hypersurface of a finsler space with (γ, β) - metric, *Journal of dynamical systems and geometric theories.*,12(1), 19-27.
- [3] T. N. Pandey and V. K. Chaubey,(2011) ,The variational problem in Lagrange space endowed with (γ, β) -metric, *International journal of pure and applied mathematics.*,71(4), 633-638,<https://doi.org/10.1080/1726037X.2014.917829>,
- [4] M. M. Numata,(1979), On Finsler space with (γ, β) -metric, *Tensor N. S.*,153-162.
- [5] D. Bao, S. S.(2000) , *An introduction to Riemannian-Fisler geometry*,Vergal New York: Springer, DOI 10.1007/978-1-4612-1268-3.
- [6] T. N. Pandey and V. K. Chaubey,(2013), On Finsler space with (γ, β) -metric Geodesic connection and scalar curvature, *Tensor N. S.*, 74, 126-134.
- [7] M. Matsumoto and S. Numata,(1979), On Finsler space with cubic metric, *Tensor N. S.*, 33, 153-162.
- [8] T. N. Pandey and V. K. Chaubey,(2011) , Theory of Finsler space with (γ, β) -metrics, *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasova*, 4(53),43-56.
- [9] M.Matsumoto,(1986) .,Foundation of Finsler Geometry and Spacial Finsler Spaces, *Kaiseisha Press Saikawa, Otsu,Japan*,<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/000839756>.
- [10] M. Hashiguchi,(1976), On conformal transformation of Finsler metrics, *J. Math. Kyoto University*,16, 25-50.
- [11] A. Tayebi, M. Shahbazi Nai,(2019), On conformally flat fourth root (α, β) -metrics, *Diff. Geom. Appl.*, 62, 253-266.
- [12] S. I. Amari, H. Nagaoka,(2000), Methods of Information Geometry,*AMS Transformation of Math. Monographs, Oxford University Press.*

On Conformal Transformation of Lagrange Space with (γ, β) -Metric

- [13] Z. Shen,(2006), Riemannian-Finsler geometry with applications to information geometry, *Chin. Ann. Math.* 27, 73-94.